

Guidelines and Style for IRRN contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2.3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Viviparous seed germination in rice varieties at Maruteru

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In coastal Andhra Pradesh, Mahsuri, the most popularly grown variety, has almost gone out of cultivation because of viviparous seed germination during kharif when rains occur at harvest or when the plants lodge into standing water because of high winds.

To screen for viviparous germination, 25 rice varieties were grown during 1982 kharif under normal conditions at 20- × 15-cm spacing with a fertilizer schedule of 40-13-25 kg NPK/ha.

Viviparous seed germination in Maruteru rices.

Strong	Moderate	Weak
MTU4392 MTU5195 MTU2716 MTU6182 MTU5182	MTU10, MTU19, MTU4569, MTU3, MTU3626, MTU7030, MTU7029, MTU7633, MTU5196, MTU5249	MTU6024, MTU11, MTU8089, MTU8002, MTU23, MTU5194, MTU8, MTU13, MTU4870, MTU16

Mature panicles were collected and kept in trays filled with soil. Conditions for seed germination were created by maintaining water saturation level in the trays. Temperatures ranged from 23-25°C to 28-31°C. Varieties were classified into 3 germination capacity groups: strong (80-94% germination), moderate (more than 20% germination), and weak (0-5% germination).

Ten varieties exhibited weak viviparous germination and can be safely grown during kharif (see table). MTU8002, MTU8089, and MTU4870 already are widely grown. Among the moderate varieties, MTU7029 occupies 50% of the area in coastal A.P. All long-duration kharif varieties tested had lower viviparous germination than Mahsuri (80% germination at maturity). ■

Rice ratooning in West Bengal

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In the low-lying marshy areas of West Bengal, two rice crops, kharif (Jul-Nov) and boro (Jan-May), are grown. During the rainy season, 50-100 cm stagnant water caused by impeded drainage cuts productivity and the high-yielding varieties do not show an advantage over local varieties.

Maintaining a continuous crop (through ratooning) was tested with

two high-yielding varieties (IR36 and IR50) and two photoperiod-sensitive varieties (CR1014 and Kumragore) that can stand semideep water lodging. Seedlings were transplanted in Jan with 4 fertilizer treatments (100 kg N, 100-22 kg NP/ha, 100-42 kg NK/ha, and 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha) in a split-plot design with 4 replications. All ratoon plots received 20 kg N/ha at main crop harvest and 10 kg N/ha at 60 d.

IR50 and IR36 started putting forth ratoon panicles 30 d after main crop harvest. Mature panicles were picked at 15- to 20-d intervals. A number of